

LIDAR Data Management: Interpolating a Selected Area of a LiDAR Point Cloud into a Raster in SGIS v.R

Elena Gjorgjieva; Kiro Gjorgjiev
elena@simplegissoft.com ; kiro@simplegissoft.com ; info@simplegissoft.com

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Sometimes, we need to focus on a specific area of a LiDAR point cloud to create a raster, like a DEM or DTM. By narrowing down to just a portion of the data, you can save processing time and ease the load on your computer's resources.

Let's dive into how this is done in SGIS v.R.

Fig.1 Importing a LAS file into SGIS v.R.

Fig.2 In this example, we first imported a LiDAR LAS file into SGIS v.R, followed by the Polygon layer, which represents the specific area to be rasterized.

Fig.3 For clearer visualization in this demonstration, we've selected and highlighted the polygon feature. It appears in the graphics panel as an outlined area—it's a polygon, not a polyline. If users have a polyline instead, they can easily convert it to a polygon with a single click using the 'Close Polyline' tool.

Once the LAS data is loaded, we'll bring in the Polygon SHP layer. This polygon outlines the specific area we want to interpolate to a raster in our example.

Next, we need to find 'Create Grid' and click on it.

Fig.4 After importing the LAS file and the Polygon Layer representing the area to be interpolated, we move on by clicking the 'Create Grid' function.

Fig.5 In this step, instead of selecting 'All Points' as in the previous example, we choose the layer representing the Polygon Area from the dropdown menu.

In the Interpolation dialog window, we need to adjust a few settings. First, we'll set the Interpolation Grid Step to 0.25m, the Distance Power to 2, and Min. Points to 3.

Instead of selecting 'All Points' like in the previous example, we'll now choose the layer with the Polygon Area from the dropdown menu and click on it. The rest of the settings will stay the same.

Finally, we'll click 'Interpolate' to proceed.

Fig.6 The remaining settings are left unchanged. We finalize the process by clicking 'Interpolate' to proceed.

The DEM Hillshade is generated and displayed in the Layers Panel.

Fig.7 The DEM Hillshade is generated and displayed in the Layers Panel.

This Hillshade can be easily exported as a TIFF, PNG, or JPG file.

To highlight the area, we've overlaid a basemap with the polygon area, allowing us to visualize its location and the surrounding terrain features.

Fig.8 To highlight the area, a basemap is overlaid with the polygon area, enabling us to visualize its location and the surrounding terrain features.

Fig.9 The 0.25m grid step hillshade accurately reflects the terrain features, while the basemap offers a precise representation of the landscape, allowing us to verify that they align correctly.

We'll repeat the process, this time using the Ground Classification points to create a DTM for the selected area.

First, we'll export the Ground points into a new layer in the Layers panel. To do this, we select Classification code 2 from the LIDAR toolbox, then close the toolbox and activate the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function.

Once the Ground points are separated, we'll open the Interpolation dialog window again and adjust the settings as needed.

Fig.10 We repeat the process using the Ground Classification points to create a DTM. The Ground points are exported into a new layer by selecting Classification code 2 from the LIDAR toolbox and using the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function.

In the same way, we'll set the grid step to 0.25m, the distance power to 2, and the Min. Points to 3. Since we're using the same Interpolation Polygon area, we'll select the 'Interpolation Polygon' layer from the dropdown list. With more layers now in the Layers Panel, these are reflected in the dropdown options. Once everything is set, we'll click 'Interpolate' to proceed.

Fig.11 After finalizing the settings, we click 'Interpolate' to proceed.

Fig.12 The DTM Hillshade is generated in just 86 milliseconds.

The DTM hillshade is generated in 859 milliseconds, as shown in the information bar at the bottom of the user interface. It can be exported as a raster file in TIFF, JPG, or PNG format for further processing. With that, the procedure is complete.

Fig.13 The procedure is complete.